

1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition of Aryl Nitrile Oxides to 5-Spirostenes

ABDUL U. SIDDIQUI*, A. H. SIDDIQUI and T. SUNDARA RAMAIAH

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 001

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Several biological activities have been found to be associated with extranuclear heterosteroids with isoxazole or isoxazoline ring fused in different positions of steroidal ring system¹. In continuation of our work on steroidal isoxazolines², we report here synthesis of extranuclear isoxazolines of spirostane series by 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of aryl nitrile oxides to the C₅ - C₆ double bond of 5-spirostenes.

Steroidal-5-enes, (25*R*)-5-spirosten-3β-ol (1a), (25*R*)-5-spirosten-3β-yl acetate (1b), (25*R*)-3β-chloro-

5-spirostene (1c), (25*R*)-5-spirostene (1d), (25*R*)-5-spirosten-3β-methyl ether (1e) and (25*R*)-spirosten-3β-ethyl ether (1f) were reacted with aryl nitrile oxides, benzonitrile oxides, *p*-methoxybenzonitrile oxide, *p*-methylbenzonitrile oxide and *p*-chlorobenzonitrile oxide (prepared *in situ*³) to afford the isoxazoline derivatives (2a-x) (Table 1). The isoxazoline derivatives may have either structure 2 or 3. The characterisation of cycloaddition product as (25*R*)-spirostan-3'-aryl-[5,6-*d*]-2'-isoxazoline (2) was based on spectral

*Present address : Department of Biochemistry, Rice University, P.O. Box 1892, Houston, TX-77251, U.S.A.

- 1
 1a; R=OH d; R=H
 b; R=CH₃COO e; R=OCH₃
 c; R=Cl f; R=OC₂H₅

- 2
 2-3a, g, m, s; R=OH
 b, h, n, t; R=CH₃COO
 c, i, o, u; R=Cl
 d, j, p, v; R=H
 e, k, q, w; R=OCH₃
 f, l, r, x; R=OC₂H₅

- 3
 2-3a-f; Ar=Ph
 g-l; Ar=Ph.OMe
 m-r; Ar=Ph.CH₃
 s-x; Ar=Ph Cl

data, $\nu_{\max}$ 1 640, 1 600 (C=C), 1 480 (C=N), 1 250 (C-O) and 690 cm^{-1} (N-O); δ 7.4-7.6 (m, 4-5 ArH of benzene or substituted benzene ring), 5.1-5.3 (1H, m, C₆- β H)⁴ and 4.2-4.6 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 10-12 Hz, C₃- α H)⁵. The appearance of C₆- β H at δ 5.1-5.3 at considerable downfield is attributed to the presence of adjacent oxygen of isoxazoline ring, the C₆-H is deshielded. In the alternate structure (3) where no oxygen is present in proximity with C₆-H, the chemical shift of C₆-H would be expected to be in the region of δ 2-3. Hence on the basis of pmr spectra the alternate structure 3 is ruled out. In the above 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition, reactions *p*-methoxybenzoxonitrile oxide gave better yields of the isoxazoline derivatives.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a

Varian A-60 instrument with TMS as internal standard. Physical and spectral data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a-x

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	$\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	δ
2a	138-39	3 420 (OH), 1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 490 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 680 (N-O)	7.56 (5H, m, ArH), 5.35 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.48 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 10 Hz, C ₃ - α H)
b	103-05	1 720 (CH ₃ COO), 1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 680 (N-O)	7.48 (5H, m, ArH), 5.28 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.45 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 2.08 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO)
c	114-15	1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 670 (N-O), 560 (C-Cl)	7.52 (5H, m, ArH), 5.30 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.38 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 10 Hz, C ₃ - α H)
d	126-27	1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 490 (C=N), 1 250 (C-O), 680 (N-O)	7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 5.28 (1H, m, C ₆ - β H)
e	220-22	1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 245 (C-O), 670 (N-O)	7.56 (5H, m, ArH), 5.35 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.48 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 11 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 3.40 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
f	243-45	1 640, 1 600 (C=C), 1 490 (C=N), 1 245 (C-O), 690 (N-O)	7.56 (5H, m, ArH), 5.35 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.48 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 3.2 (2H, q, OCH ₂), 1.50 (3H, s, CH ₃ of OC ₂ H ₅)
g	201-02	3 420 (OH), 1 640, 1 600 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 250 (C-O), 690 (N-O)	7.60 (4H, m, ArH), 5.30 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.42 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 3.68 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃)
h	190-91	1 725 (CH ₃ COO), 1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 490 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 680 (N-O)	7.56 (4H, m, ArH), 5.20 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.38 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 10 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 2.1 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO), 3.68 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃)
i	178-79	1 640, 1 590 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 670 (N-O), 580 (C-Cl)	7.62 (4H, m, ArH), 5.28 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.36 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 3.62 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃)
j	182-84	1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 490 (C=N), 1 250 (C-O), 690 (N-O)	7.48 (4H, m, ArH), 5.30 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 3.65 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃)
k	226-28	1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 470 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 670 (N-O)	7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 5.25 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.40 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 11 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 3.65 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃), 3.35 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
l	234-36	1 620, 1 590 (C=C), 1 480 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 680 (N-O)	7.46 (4H, m, ArH), 5.35 (1H, dd, C ₆ - β H), 4.38 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 10 Hz, C ₃ - α H), 3.60 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃), 3.15 (2H, q, OCH ₂), 1.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ of OC ₂ H ₅)

(Table 1 contd.)

m	194-95	3 450 (OH), 1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 250 (C-O), 690 (N-O)	7.40 (4H, m, ArH), 5.25 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.35 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 12 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃)
n	180-82	1 720 (CH ₃ COO), 1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 490 (C=N), 1 245 (C-O), 690 (N-O)	7.56 (4H, m, ArH), 5.30 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.38 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 11 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 2.30 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 2.15 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO)
o	196-97	1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 490 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 680 (N-O), 560 (C-Cl)	7.46 (4H, m, ArH), 5.24 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.32 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 10 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 2.28 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃)
p	190-91	1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 250 (C-O), 670 (N-O)	7.60 (4H, m, ArH), 5.28 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 2.25 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃)
q	218-20	1 620, 1 600 (C=C), 1 480 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 670 (N-O)	7.42 (4H, m, ArH), 5.40 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.32 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 12 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 2.30 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.35 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
r	226-28	1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 680 (N-O)	7.36 (4H, m, ArH), 5.35 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.38 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 10 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 2.28 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.30 (2H, q, OCH ₂), 1.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ of OC ₂ H ₅)
s	184-85	3 460 (OH), 1 620, 1 600 (C=C), 1 480 (C=N), 1 245 (C-O), 690 (N-O), 600 (C-Cl)	7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 5.30 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.38 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 10 Hz, C ₃ -αH)
t	156-57	1 725 (CH ₃ COO), 1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 250 (C-O), 670 (N-O), 590 (C-Cl)	7.46 (4H, m, ArH), 5.28 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.30 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 11 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 2.15 (3H, s, CH ₃ COO)
u	172-73	1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 480 (C=N), 1 240 (C-O), 690 (N-O), 570 (C-Cl)	7.44 (4H, m, ArH), 5.38 (1H, m, C ₆ -βH), 4.30 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 10 Hz, C ₃ -αH)
v	163-64	1 620, 1 590 (C=C), 1 480 (C=N), 1 245 (C-O), 680 (N-O)	7.60 (4H, m, ArH), 5.40 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH)
w	212-14	1 630, 1 600 (C=C), 1 500 (C=N), 1 245 (C-O), 670 (N-O), 590 (C-Cl)	7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 5.36 (1H, m, C ₆ -βH), 4.38 (1H, m, W _{1/2} , 12 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 3.42 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
x	238-39	1 640, 1 610 (C=C), 1 480 (C=N), 1 245 (C-O), 680 (N-O), 590 (C-Cl)	7.66 (4H, m, ArH), 5.42 (1H, dd, C ₆ -βH), 4.40 (1H, W _{1/2} , 12 Hz, C ₃ -αH), 3.25 (2H, q, OCH ₂), 1.40 (3H, s, CH ₃ of OC ₂ H ₅)

*All these compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Aryl hydroxamic acid chloride: Aromatic aldehyde (10 g) was suspended in aqueous sodium hydroxide (38% ; 250 ml) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (8 g) was added to it in small portions with constant stirring. Then stirring was continued further for 30 min and carbon dioxide was passed through the solution until it became saturated. The resultant oxime was filtered, suspended in 8N HCl (100 ml) at 0° and chlorine gas was bubbled through it until bluish green colour produced in the beginning disappeared. The benzhydroxamic acid chloride thus obtained was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous) and evaporation of ether gave the product (7.5 g ; ~70%).

(25R)-Spirostan-3'-aryl-[5,6-d]-2'-isoxazoline (2a-x). A typical procedure: To a solution of the (25R)-5-spirostene (1 ; 1.2 mmol) in benzene-ether (1 : 1 ; 30 ml) was added an ethereal solution of aryl nitrile oxide (generated *in situ* by shaking an ethereal solution of 9.6 mmol benzhydroxamic acid chloride³ with 100 ml aqueous 10% NaOH at 0° and then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄). The mixture was stirred at 0-5° in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 h, then warmed on a water-bath (55-60°). Removal of the solvent gave a solid which was crystallised from methanol to yield the product. The compounds (64-90%) were found to be homogeneous on tlc (ether-benzene, 2 : 3).

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